

[Andersen](#), T., [Andersson](#), U. B., [Graham](#), S., [Åberg](#), G. & [Simonsen](#), S. L. Granitic magmatism by melting of juvenile continental crust: new constraints on the source of Palaeoproterozoic granitoids in Fennoscandia from Hf isotopes in zircon. *J. Geol. Soc. Lond.* 166, 233–247 (2009).

[Battisti](#), M. A., [Bitencourt](#), M. F., [Nardi](#), L. V. S., [Florisbal](#), L. M., [Sláma](#), J., [Ackerman](#), L. & [Padilha](#), D. F. Unravelling major magmatic episodes from metamorphic sequences of the Dom Feliciano Belt central sector, Brazil – a comparative study of geochronology, elemental geochemistry, and Sr-Nd data. *Precambrian Res.* 385, 106951 (2023).

[Battisti](#), M. A., [Konopásek](#), J., [Bitencourt](#), M. F., [Sláma](#), J., [Percival](#), J. J., [De Toni](#), G. B., [Silva](#), S. C., [Costa](#), E. O. & [Trubac](#), J. Petrochronology of the Dom Feliciano Belt foreland in southernmost Brazil reveals two distinct tectonometamorphic events in the western central Kaoko–Dom Feliciano–Gariiep orogen. *Int. J. Earth Sci.* (2024).

[Hoerlle](#), G. S., [Remus](#), M. V. D. & [Dani](#), N. Metamafic dyke and sill swarms in the Dom Feliciano Belt: Insights for post-collisional strike-slip tectonics and fluid-assisted metamorphism, Southern Brazil. *Precambrian Res.* 383, 106906 (2022).

[Hoerlle](#), G. S., [Remus](#), M. V. D., [Müller](#), T., [Piazolo](#), S., [Lana](#), C. & [Sorger](#), D. Metasomatic reactions triggered by localized and dynamically evolving fluid flux multistage intrusion history: an example from the syntectonic Caçapava do Sul Granitic Complex, Southern Brazil. *Lithos* 442–443, 107103 (2023).

[Leite](#), J. A. D., [Hartmann](#), L. A., [McNaughton](#), N. J. & [Chemale Jr](#), F. SHRIMP U/Pb zircon geochronology of Neoproterozoic juvenile and crustal-reworked terranes in southernmost Brazil. *Int. Geol. Rev.* 40, 688–705 (1998).

[Madruga](#), D. R., [Remus](#), M. V. D., [Hoerlle](#), G. S., [Mazoz](#), A. O., [Lana](#), C. C. & [Dani](#), N. Unraveling the polymetamorphism of calc-silicate rocks using titanite, zircon and apatite U–Pb geochronology and Zr-in-titanite thermometry. *Lithos* 488–489, 107822 (2024).

[Nardi](#), L. V. S. & [Bitencourt](#), M. F. Geologia, petrologia e geoquímica do Complexo Granítico Caçapava do Sul, RS. *Rev. Bras. Geociencias* 19, 153–269 (1989).

[Remus](#), M. V. D., [Hartmann](#), L. A., [McNaughton](#), N. J., [Groves](#), D. I. & [Fletcher](#), I. R. The link between hydrothermal epigenetic copper mineralization and the Caçapava Granite of the Brasiliano Cycle in Southern Brazil. *J. S. Am. Earth Sci.* 13, 191–216 (2000).

[UFRGS](#). Mapeamento geológico 1:50.000 de parte das folhas Passo do Salsinho SH.22-Y-A-I-4 (MI-2982/4) e Arroio Santa Bárbara SH.22-Y-A-I-3 (MI-2982/3). Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre (1998).